

1 **Microplastic aging processes: environmental relevance and analytical implications**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 The analysis of microplastics (MPs) in terrestrial environments and the evaluation of their
14 environmental risk has gained great attention, owing to the increasing evidence for their widespread
15 presence in soils and freshwater sediments globally. Once in the environment, MPs undergo abiotic
16 and biotic processes which alter their properties and integrity: this process is called “aging” and has
17 implications for the fate of these contaminants, their morphology and surface chemistry. Aging may
18 also affect the analytical assessment of MPs in environmental samples: environmental samples likely
19 contain aged MPs, while analytical methods are generally established using pristine plastics for
20 validation. This can lead to uncertainties in quantification and characterization. This critical review
21 summarizes the current trends in the simulation and characterization of MP aging in laboratory
22 conditions, highlighting limitations and knowledge gaps. It also discusses the challenges in MP
23 analysis induced by aging in environmental samples, providing directions towards possible solutions.

24

25 **Graphical abstract**

26

27

28 **Keywords**

29 MP; degradation; weathering; analytical protocol; biofilm; leaching; environmental sample; polymer.

30

31 **Abbreviations**

32 AFM atomic force microscopy

33 BET Brunauer Emmett Teller

34 CLSM confocal laser scanning microscopy

35 DNA deoxyribonucleic acid

36 EDX energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy

37 EGA evolved gas analysis

38 EPS extracellular polymeric substances

39 FTIR Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy

40 GC gas chromatography

41 H_2O_2 hydrogen peroxide

42 ICP-MS inductively coupled plasma - mass spectrometry

43 KOH potassium hydroxide

- 44 LA laser ablation
- 45 LIBS laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
- 46 MALDI-ToF-MS matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry
- 47 MP microplastic
- 48 MS mass spectrometry
- 49 NaOH sodium hydroxide
- 50 PE polyethylene
- 51 PET polyethylene terephthalate
- 52 PLA polylactic acid
- 53 PP polypropylene
- 54 PVC polyvinyl chloride
- 55 PS polystyrene
- 56 Py-GC-MS pyrolysis - gas chromatography - mass spectrometry
- 57 SEM scanning electron microscopy
- 58 STXM scanning transmission X-ray microscopy
- 59 TEM transmission electron microscopy
- 60 TGA-DSC thermogravimetric analysis - differential scanning calorimetry
- 61 ToF-SIMS Time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry
- 62 UV ultraviolet
- 63 XPS X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
- 64 XRD X-ray diffraction

65 **1. Introduction**

66 Plastic pollution is an environmental threat of global relevance. Plastic, and especially microplastics
67 (MPs, fragments with dimension between 1 and 1000 μm [1]), are widespread in the environment.
68 Nine to 23 million metric tons of plastic are estimated to reach the oceans every year [2]. However,
69 this represents less than 3% of total mismanaged plastic waste [3]. In contrast, the load of mismanaged
70 plastic released to land and freshwaters is tenfold higher (30% of the total[4]). This load accumulates
71 primarily in freshwater sediments and soils. The broader environmental impacts of this
72 contamination, however, remain unclear [5–8].

73 Once plastic is dispersed in these compartments it undergoes a series of processes collectively
74 resulting in aging (this process is also referred to as weathering or degradation). These processes may
75 be divided into two main categories: abiotic and biotic processes. The former includes reactions with
76 physical-chemical agents affecting polymer matrix integrity and chemistry (e.g., light irradiation,
77 physical abrasion, thermo-chemical oxidation), while the latter includes the processes leading to the
78 formation of a “corona” (or biofilm) of microorganisms [9,10]. While biotic and abiotic aging
79 processes act simultaneously, the prevalence of a given process can in theory vary upon the
80 environment in which plastic is dispersed (e.g., in different environmental matrices) and the chemical
81 composition of the plastic [5,10]. All these processes alter the surface properties, reactivity,
82 propensity to embrittlement, and more generally the environmental fate (and possibly toxicity) of
83 plastic fragments [5,11,12]. Environmental effects of MP aging have already been summarized in
84 several recent reviews (e.g., [7,10,13–18]).

85 Beyond the changes in behavior and characteristics of plastic in an environmental context, its
86 alteration induced by aging processes carries a series of implications for the analytical methods used
87 to purify, concentrate, and analyze MPs in environmental samples. Setting up analytical protocols
88 and harmonization of MP analyses of environmental samples – and especially carbon rich sediments
89 and soils – have represented a challenging endeavor. Methods need to provide high reliability,

90 sensitivity, and effectiveness while facing the daunting heterogeneity in polymer types, chemical
91 additives, shapes, and sizes characterizing the particles present in environmental samples [19,20]. In
92 addition, MP analytical protocols are generally established and validated using virgin, unweathered
93 MPs, which present different physical and chemical features compared with aged environmental
94 particles [21], and which can be difficult to accurately reproduce in standard reference materials used
95 for method validation. This adds further additional challenges and implications for analysis which, to
96 date, have not been sufficiently addressed.

97 In this critical review, we will first summarize the environmental processes related to aging and the
98 best strategies to create simulated aged materials. We will then review environmental implications of
99 MP aging, with a focus on the knowledge gaps and the available analytical tools to characterize the
100 effects of aging processes on MP properties. Finally, we will examine the main implications for the
101 analytical assessment of MPs in real environmental samples associated to their aging. We will
102 conclude by proposing ways forward to overcome some of these issues.

103

104 **2. Aging processes and their experimental simulation**

105 The simulation of environmental processes and agents affecting MP weathering is a key step toward
106 the understanding of MP environmental aging and the creation of environmentally realistic standard
107 reference materials. Aged MP reference materials may be used for method validation, quality
108 assurance and control, as well as for use in fate and effect studies.

109 Aging processes are generally simulated in simplified laboratory conditions or through long-term
110 semi- or un-controlled field exposures. These processes in the environment vary based on the
111 conditions in which MPs are generated or dispersed: the different aging agents can in fact act
112 differently (e.g., light exposure is different along depth in the water column or in soil environments).
113 Aging experiments are typically designed to cover specific environments and aging processes [22].
114 Here we will review aging studies for terrestrial natural environments (i.e., freshwaters and soils).

115

116 **2.1. Laboratory-based aging studies**

117 Laboratory based methods to simulate MP aging are adapted from engineering studies to assess
118 plastic durability. The main approach used in these experiments is ultraviolet (UV) irradiation to
119 simulate the photoinduced oxidation of plastic polymers due to sunlight exposure [15,16]. This
120 process is simulated in a wide range of conditions, varying from exposure in air or different
121 environmental media (e.g., freshwater, sand, etc.) and at various radiation intensities, durations, and
122 temperatures [23]. Polymer oxidation can also be simulated with other physical and chemical
123 stressors, such as ozone [22], chemical oxidants in solution (e.g., hydrogen peroxide-H₂O₂, Fenton
124 reagent, and sodium hypochlorite [24,25]), and thermally induced oxidation [26]. UV oxidation
125 experiments remain the most frequently utilized approach, likely because of the simplicity of the
126 experimental setup and the abundance of pre-existing studies in polymer engineering literature
127 [23,25]. However, some limitations arise in the use of UV oxidation processes to generate
128 environmentally relevant aged MPs. Namely, i) the variable exposure conditions tested complicates
129 the comparison of findings among different studies [23]; ii) oxidation induced by UV radiation
130 heterogeneously affects the bulk material even at constant light radiation; iii) plastic objects are
131 loaded with UV filters or other type of antioxidants to reduce the direct oxidation of the polymers
132 [27], while MPs tested are usually additive-free industrial pellets or spheres [21,23]; and iv) several
133 other stressors in the environment affect MP aging [23].

134 Besides oxidation, other aging processes which induce chemical changes in plastic (e.g., hydrolysis)
135 are also studied at the laboratory scale. Hydrolysis processes are observed to favor the scissions of
136 ester bonds in the environment [10]: this process is simulated in laboratory settings by increasing the
137 temperature or catalyzing the acidic or alkaline hydrolysis (e.g., with sodium hydroxide – NaOH or
138 nitric acid solutions [15]).

139 Chemical and physical conditions in the environment may modulate the effect of oxidation. In more
140 sophisticated experimental settings, other chemicals are used often in combination with the main
141 oxidative chemical or photochemical agent to render more realistic conditions in relation to specific
142 environments. Some examples include treatments at increasing salinity, in natural soil (vs artificial
143 soils), and with variable water chemistry [10,28]. These approaches are conceived to improve the
144 environmental relevance of the aging processes and of the obtained aged plastics. However, more
145 complex aging conditions may blur the possibility of tracking the effects of different agents, resulting
146 in a loss of information and control.

147 Mechanical stress is another abiotic agent simulated in laboratory experiments. These studies consider
148 the deployment of plastic specimens in batches with other types of solids such as silica, sand grains,
149 or sandpaper. Aging is performed by adding a frictional force, typically through shaking or sonication
150 [29,30]. This type of aging simulates important environmental factors affecting terrestrial MP (e.g.,
151 the friction during longitudinal transport in soils and burial processes in sediments). However, these
152 types of laboratory assessment are still relatively rare.

153 Finally, lab-based works have also addressed biotic aging of MPs through studies of the formation of
154 a microorganism corona on MP particle surfaces. These experiments are typically performed through
155 the incubation of MPs with artificially assembled consortia of microorganisms or inocula obtained
156 from the environment (e.g. from wastewater treatment plant sludges, or fresh- and seawater algal
157 and/or bacterial community) [28,31]. However, creating realistic biofouled MPs in a reproducible
158 manner is challenging, especially when working with assemblages of multiple species. This requires
159 tight control over nutrient concentration and pH in the growth medium, as well as temperature, light
160 availability, consistency of inocula, mixing rate of the solution, and incubation time. To reduce
161 complexity, some studies have focused on growing mono-species biofilms [28]. This can help to
162 achieve more reliable and predictable aging across different batches, but with a trade-off on the
163 environmental representativeness of the obtained MPs.

164

165 **2.2. Field-based aging studies**

166 Aging studies conducted under the field conditions initially focused on MPs in aquatic environments.
167 These were typically characterised by a lack of control over environmental conditions, with a primary
168 focus on better understanding process of biofilm formation and changes in properties and behavior
169 (e.g., buoyancy) [32]. Aging of MPs in natural waters is complicated by the occurrence of moving
170 waters or currents, which can lead to the potential loss of materials, and by several confounding
171 factors such as variable climate conditions and water currents. As a result, incubation is often
172 performed in submerged enclosures. This arrangement can in theory influence the aging process and
173 affect the results, for example by limiting light exposure of floating MPs which were forcibly
174 submerged [33].

175 Studies focusing on aging of MPs in soil ecosystems under field conditions are still lacking. The
176 effects of photo- and thermo-oxidation, heteroaggregation, transport, and biodegradation of MPs in
177 soil have so far been studied only under laboratory conditions [6,18]. This paucity of information
178 represents an important knowledge gap, particularly given that some preliminary studies have
179 indicated that the majority of MPs may be retained by some soil types (e.g., [34]) and the difficulties
180 in replicating several environmentally relevant processes in the laboratory. This has already been
181 reported, for example, with respect to differences in plastic biodegradation rates in laboratory vs field
182 experiments (e.g., [35]).

183 A clear benefit of implementing field-based studies over laboratory simulations is their ability to
184 replicate or utilize actual environmental processes. This approach clearly has a high environmental
185 relevance but, at the same time, limits the extrapolation of results to other sites: the conditions for
186 aging cannot be controlled and are highly site-specific. The high environmental realism is gained at
187 the loss of high environmental control. It has in fact already been suggested that, in order to obtain

188 generalizable results, studies should be replicated in multiple locations and in different periods of the
189 year [23].

190

191 **3. MPs changes in properties after aging: current knowledge gaps and research needs**

192 The changes induced by aging processes have implications for the potential toxicity and behavior of
193 MPs. In this section, we summarize the main trends related to alterations in plastic properties induced
194 by different aging processes, focusing on how different abiotic and biotic aging agents, alone or in
195 combination, may affect physicochemical properties of plastics, including a consideration of the
196 implications which may be expected for their study in environmental (analytical) chemistry. Within
197 the context of this review article, we will mainly focus on the knowledge gaps related to MP aging
198 effects.

199

200 **3.1. Surface chemistry**

201 Changes in surface properties are important in defining the tendency of MPs to form aggregates, as
202 well as to transport various chemical species in the environment [36]. The surface chemistry of MPs
203 also affects the sorption processes of chemical contaminants, which can in theory alter their potential
204 toxicity [5,7,37]. Hence, gaining control over the surface characteristics that influence these
205 interactions is key to understand the drivers and mechanism of MP toxicity related to the aging of
206 particles in the environment. This is also fundamental to achieve effective ecological risk assessments
207 of plastic pollution in terrestrial and freshwater settings.

208 The chemical mechanisms of photo- and thermo- oxidation and the consequential effects on surface
209 properties – especially for polyolefins (i.e., polyethylene - PE, polypropylene - PP) and other
210 conventional polymers (e.g., polystyrene - PS, polyethylene terephthalate - PET) – are well known
211 [13,25]. The surface of aged MPs is characterized by an enrichment in oxygen-containing functional
212 groups (especially carbonyl and hydroxyl groups), increased hydrophilicity, and a shift towards a

213 more negative surface charge in comparison with pristine polymers [7,16,38]. Less marked changes
214 in polyesters such as PET are ascribable to different degradation mechanisms (i.e., Norrish type I and
215 II, hydrolysis) and also to the fact that these polymers have oxygen-containing functional groups
216 already in their pristine form [10]. Data concerning changes in surface properties from chemical or
217 photo-oxidative processes in biodegradable polymers are instead scant and fragmentary. As an
218 example, UV aging of polylactic acid (PLA) has shown unclear trends in oxidation processes: while
219 some reports show that UV aging results in oxidation processes comparable with other polymers
220 (such as PE and PP), other studies find less marked changes [39,40]. A possible explanation is that
221 other processes (e.g., hydrolysis) prevail, acting at a faster rate in degrading the polymer compared
222 to photooxidation. Also, the potential different load of anti-oxidants and UV filters added to these
223 biodegradable materials can likely play a role [41].

224 The oxidation of polymers and the increase in surface oxygen-containing functional groups makes
225 MPs more prone to sorb hydrophobic compounds and metals in aquatic solutions [42,43]. These
226 changes also increase polymer wettability and the negative surface charge of MPs (Fig. 1a, [5,7]).

227 The development of a biofilm or so-called “eco-corona” on the surface of microplastics also yields
228 significant changes in the surface properties. The biofilm comprising microorganisms such as algae
229 and bacteria and their extracellular polymeric substances (EPS), lipids, or proteins completely
230 changes the surface properties of MPs, acting as a “cover effect” and masking the surface properties
231 of MPs, regardless of the polymer abiotic aging (Fig. 1 b). The surface is generally enriched in
232 peptides, hydroxyls, and polysaccharides by corona formation, while some studies reported a
233 reduction in carbonyl groups after biotic aging [7,28,40]. These changes also provide additional
234 binding sites for complexation and decrease surface hydrophobicity [44,45]. This significantly
235 changes the sorption properties for other pollutants. Ionic compounds and metals may be both
236 chemically bound in the extracellular matrix of biofilms and be actively absorbed by cellular uptake
237 mechanisms of microorganisms composing the biofilm community [5,11,40]. Hydrophobic

238 contaminants may instead passively diffuse in microbiological tissues mimicking the same process
239 happening on plastic surface, especially in the case of low-density polymer matrixes known to
240 effectively accumulate these types of substances [46–48]. However, the biological matrix may affect
241 uptake rates posing an additional resistance at the interface between the plastic and soil particles or
242 water films. For example, natural organic matter coatings on PS MPs has been shown to reduce
243 sorption of two antibiotics by blocking potential sorption sites at the surface of the plastic [49].
244 Diffusion across a biofilm formed on PE MPs was also shown to be responsible for the slower uptake
245 of tetracycline into MPs [42]. The organism composing the biofilm community may also metabolize
246 and possibly degrade the absorbed chemicals.

247 The biofilm on the surface of MPs can also be associated with initial surface physical degradation
248 causing cracks and singularities [33,50]. The presence of irregularities and cracks may further
249 increase the specific surface area of MPs, which, in turn, may increase the adsorption capacity of MPs
250 toward hydrophobic contaminants [7]. Another effect associated with the presence of biofilms is the
251 scattering of UV light that would otherwise initiate abiotic degradation. In fact, UV radiation
252 penetrates poorly into the matrix of biofilms, and only the first few top layers of microbial cells are
253 exposed [51,52]. Therefore, for MPs covered by a biofilm, exposure to UV radiation may be minimal
254 [33,52]. On the other hand, biofilm exudates may favor hydrolysis and bacteria may use plastic as a
255 carbon source: this effect has the potential to degrade the surface of MPs [53].

256

257 Fig. 1. Conceptual model of the “cover effect” of biofilm, including the relevant environmental
 258 implications, exemplified in an aquatic setting (Modified from [5], content under creative common
 259 license). In panel a), an example of environmentally aged MP without a developed biofilm is
 260 shown, with MPs exposed to light radiation and enriched in oxygen containing functional groups. In
 261 the case of biofilm covered MP (panel b), instead, the surface functional groups of the biofilm
 262 dominate the chemical interactions, and the biofilm may “cover” the effect of light, as well as
 263 mediate sorption and leaching processes.

264

265 3.2. Effect of aging on mechanical properties and fragmentation

266 The aging processes (especially abiotic ones) are the main promoters of MP fragmentation. The
 267 plastic embrittlement and the loss of mechanical properties is due to the polymer chain scissions and

268 heterogeneities induced; for example, by photochemical aging or by biodegradation [54]. The
269 polymer type and chemical additive composition is believed to be a determinant of the propensity for
270 embrittlement under environmental stress. For example, PP is observed to be more prone to
271 embrittlement after the physicochemical oxidation of the polymer matrix compared to PE, PET, PS,
272 and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) [55]. Mechanical resistance and the physical characteristics of
273 biodegradable plastics are particularly sensitive to aging treatments under both field or laboratory
274 conditions in comparison to polyolefins [56]. However, a direct comparison of different polymers is
275 difficult to perform in a meaningful way due to different experimental processes, as well as different
276 formulations of plastic tested for aging (e.g., variable loadings of additives and polymer post-
277 processes for plastic objects production).

278 The role of abiotic aging on the fragmentation rate of plastics still presents substantial knowledge
279 gaps. The formation of MP from aged meso- and macroscopic items is a key process controlling
280 sources and concentrations of MP in the environment (e.g., [29,57–59]). However, the degradation
281 pattern of generated MPs in the environment is still unclear. Hypothetically, fragmentation of MP
282 into smaller debris results in higher reactive surface area and possibly further promotes fragmentation.
283 On the other hand, fragmentation rates may decrease after reaching a small critical size: smaller
284 fragments are expected to require stronger mechanic energy or specific mechanic stress routes (e.g.
285 by interaction with solids with adequate small roughness scale) to be further mechanically fragmented
286 [60,61]. Also, biotic aging may be limited under a critical small size threshold, in which living
287 microorganisms can no longer be stably hosted on the fragment surface. In summary, while
288 progressively smaller sizes can enhance the effectiveness of photochemical degradation processes,
289 they may hinder mechanical and biological degradation processes.

290 Biofilm formation has a significant effect on the mechanical properties of MPs, as the coverage by
291 the biofilm reduces the roughness of the MP surface and thus reduces their abrasive properties [11].
292 In addition, MPs can form complex heteroaggregates with other plastic particles or with natural

293 particulates through biofilm formation [44,62]. This increases their size but also changes the overall
294 particle density, as the density of natural biofilms and particles ranges from 1.1 to 1.5 g/cm³ [63,64],
295 while plastic polymer densities are generally lower (e.g., PE and PP range between 0.9 and 0.95
296 g/cm³) or in fewer cases higher (e.g., PVC ranges between 1.1 and 1.6 g/cm³). Such changes are
297 particularly important for MP fate and transport processes. In aquatic environments, they can change
298 the rate of deposition and accumulation in sediments or affect the longitudinal transport [64]. In soils
299 these variations in potential buoyancy can determine the efficiency of vertical (leaching) or lateral
300 (runoff) transport.

301

302 **3.3. Aging and chemical additives leaching**

303 Changes in the polymer matrix induced by abiotic aging can affect the leaching of additives and
304 monomers, as well as other compounds derived by polymer degradation. This in turn can have
305 implications for particle toxicological properties. This process is favored after the polymer aging
306 owing to polymer oxidation and further fragmentation, increasing surface area and wettability. The
307 increased wettability of polymers permits a further interaction of the water with the polymer matrix,
308 possibly enhancing leaching rates. These aspects have already been the subject of several studies [65–
309 67].

310 The plastic polymer contains various chemical types with different molecular dimensions and
311 chemical properties and, consequently, variable leaching rates. For instance, metals are often present
312 as salts, oxides, and metal-organics, which are more likely to be released in the aquatic phase
313 compared to hydrophobic chemicals, owing to their smaller molecular dimensions and possibly
314 weaker interactions especially with aliphatic polymer matrixes [68,69]. It should be also considered
315 that different chemicals present in the polymer matrix may be oxidized by UV radiation too: the
316 perfect example for this class of compounds are UV filters or anti-oxidants, which are designed to
317 absorb UV radiation and reduce the aging process of plastic polymers or prevent oxidation of the

318 polymer chain by reacting themselves with oxygen radicals or radicals produced by the initiation of
319 the polymer chain fracture. Oxidation makes these compounds more hydrophilic (e.g., [70]) and
320 therefore also possibly more prone to leaching. Other additives (e.g., flame retardants) can also be
321 oxidized and become more prone to leaching in water [17]. This evidence highlights the importance
322 of understanding aging mechanisms and considering the chemical composition of aged particles when
323 studying MP toxicity.

324 Despite the extensive literature dealing with leaching of additives during abiotic aging, knowledge
325 on the effects of biotic aging on leaching is much more limited [12]. The role of the eco-corona
326 covering MPs is unclear: on one side it may mediate the release of chemicals from plastic, inducing,
327 on the other side, a faster biodegradation of the polymer. As an example, the potential release of
328 plastic-borne dissolved organic matter through leaching from environmental plastics has been
329 observed, as well as the ability of this leachate to alter the bacterial community in experiments
330 conducted with lake water [71]. This process may lead to the assemblage of a plastic-specific biofilm
331 community, which likely selects organisms using plastic leachate as a carbon source [50]. On the
332 other hand, toxic additives released by aged plastics can also reduce the colonization by sensitive
333 microorganisms: abiotically aged MPs are in fact colonized to a limited degree by microorganisms
334 after abiotic aging. This is ascribed to the leaching of toxic chemicals after aging [40,72].

335 It is also not clear how the dynamics of leaching may change after the colonization of MP particles
336 by biofilms (Fig. 1 b). The biofilm may act as a barrier at the surface of the MP particle influencing
337 the (kinetics of) exchange of chemicals: it was observed to stop the leaching of metallic additives
338 from plastic, both through the analysis of metal desorption in solution [48] and by the analysis of
339 metals directly in the plastic matrix of pristine and biotically aged MPs [73]. Beside this “cover
340 effect”, the use of plastic as a carbon source by the biofilm community and several compounds related
341 to biofilm formation (e.g., algal exudates) can further increase MP degradation [53], leading to higher
342 leaching rates. These aspects need specific attention in future studies of MP biotic aging.

343

344 **4. Analytical methods to assess MP aging**

345 A wide range of analytical techniques has been used to assess the aging of MPs, depending on the
346 different aging processes and analyzed properties. In the following paragraphs, we critically review
347 these techniques. The list of methods and analytical endpoints is given in Table 1.

348

349 **4.1. Analytical characterization of abiotic aging**

350 Mechanical and surface properties of MPs can be analyzed by a range of techniques. The static tensile
351 strength is the most commonly used approach to assess the changes in mechanical properties of plastic
352 after aging: it is analyzed through the use of a dynamometer, adding a continuous force on
353 macroscopic plastic fragments with a specific size and a dumbbell shape [26,74]. The variation of
354 plastic surface hydrophobicity is another technique used to assess changes on plastic surface
355 chemistry. Hydrophobicity is typically studied through contact angle and zeta potential measurements
356 [28]. A more detailed characterization of aspects concerning surface chemistry, and chemical-
357 physical properties can instead be achieved using microscopy, spectroscopy, and thermal analyses
358 [75].

359 Changes in the size, shape, and surface features (formation of cracks, pits, and holes due to oxidative
360 processes and mechanical stress) of MPs can be observed by microscopy techniques, such as optical
361 and scanning/transmission electron microscopy (SEM/TEM, Fig. 2) [28]. Electron microscopy
362 techniques can be coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) to provide local
363 semiquantitative information on the near-surface (sampling depth of few microns) elemental
364 composition of MPs and potential reveal the presence of additives (e.g., catalysts) in a non-destructive
365 way [76]. Detailed morphological information can be gained also by atomic force microscopy (AFM
366 [77]). This approach can provide topographic imaging at the nanoscale resolution, enabling
367 morphological investigation at a nanoscopic scale (Fig. 2 e-g) and a quantitative analysis of the

368 increase of surface roughness following aging, as well as the recognition of nanosized fragments
369 produced during degradation. Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) is applied as well: it
370 permits micrometric scale resolution and the recognition of chemical markers (e.g., specific polymer
371 types or adsorbed compounds) through fluorescence analysis [78]. Beyond the qualitative
372 morphological characterization of the surface, the increase in surface area after degradation of the
373 amorphous phase of polymers has been considered as a measurement that can correlate to the degree
374 of aging. This can be done using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method based on a measure of
375 the gas adsorption on the plastic surface [37,43].

376

377 Fig. 2. Examples of microscopy applications to analyze abiotic and biotic aging on PE. a-b) SEM
378 micrographs of pristine (a) and UV aged (b) PE fragments (adapted from [39] ,copyright permission
379 from Elsevier). c-d) SEM micrographs of field aged PE samples without (c) and with (d) a
380 developed biofilm on plastic surface (adapted from [79] and [80], contents under creative common
381 license). e-g) example of AFM topography used to assess the roughness before (e) and after 30 (f)
382 and 60 (g) days of mechanical aging with sand (adapted from [30], copyright permission from
383 Elsevier).

384

385 Spectroscopy techniques, such as Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Raman
386 spectroscopy, are non-destructive techniques enabling the assessment of changes in surface functional
387 groups (for example, deriving from their oxidation). These analyses are often conducted in addition
388 to optical microscopy [10,25].

389 In the context of assessing aging of MPs, it is important to obtain measurements of the differences
390 between surface and bulk material properties, as typically aging proceeds from the surface.
391 Attenuated total reflectance analysis using FTIR can help in highlighting surface modifications after
392 aging. With a smaller sampling depth (usually $< 10 \mu\text{m}$), this technique can yield data on surface
393 chemistry in a more accurate and sensitive way compared to other analytical modes.

394 The spectra obtained by Raman and FTIR measurements can be treated to highlight specific bands
395 typical of polymer aging. Specific band indexes are often used as they permit a quantitative
396 assessment of the aging of the polymer matrix. These are usually presented as ratios between oxygen
397 containing functional groups (e.g., carbonyl and hydroxyl groups) and reference peaks selected
398 depending on the analyzed polymer [15]. Moreover, Raman and FTIR spectroscopy can give insights
399 on the crystalline phase of polymers and their changes induced by aging. This information can also
400 be obtained by X-ray diffraction (XRD) [81,82].

401 Information regarding the chemical composition of the outer surface (e.g., in the range of nanometers
402 from the surface) can be achieved by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The alteration of C 1s
403 and O 1s signals can be attributed to hydroxyl, carbonyl, and carbon-oxygen functionalities generated
404 by the oxidation/hydrolysis-induced chain scissions [43]. This technique permits a more detailed
405 analysis of surface oxidation (especially when induced in laboratory experiments) in comparison to
406 FTIR measurements, since oxidation processes (and especially UV induced oxidation) primarily
407 affect the top layer of the polymer matrix [83]. While being less representative of the surface
408 oxidation, FTIR is still more commonly used as a reference technique owing to its easier operation,
409 lower costs, and higher diffusion.

410 Thermo-analytical approaches are also emerging as tools to analyze MP aging. Thermogravimetric
411 analysis and differential scanning calorimetry (TGA-DSC) can be used to assess changes in the
412 thermal stability and melting behavior of MPs. The measure of these changes can give useful insights
413 to assess polymer crystallinity [84]. The combination of thermal degradation processes with gas
414 chromatography (GC) and/or mass spectrometry (MS) analysis represents a great potential for
415 detailed quantitative and qualitative chemical analysis of the bulk material. The most commonly
416 adopted approach relies on pyrolysis (Py-GC-MS) at high temperatures (500-650°C) under anoxic
417 conditions to volatilize the polymer [85]. Volatile species separated by GC can be analyzed in MS,
418 which has the potential for providing high resolution data on the changes in the chemical composition
419 of the plastic during degradation [74,86,87]. Other thermo-analytical and/or mass-based methods are
420 applied in this research area, such as evolved gas analysis-MS (EGA-MS [65]) and matrix-assisted
421 laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight MS (MALDI-ToF-MS [88]). The latter exploits a soft
422 ionization and can overcome the limitation of the narrow mass range of GC-MS (often insufficient to
423 analyze high molecular weight compounds).

424 All thermal degradation-based strategies result, however, in the destruction of plastic samples
425 hindering the determination of the particle size and shape. Time-of-flight secondary ion mass

426 spectrometry (ToF-SIMS) is a surface analysis technique that offers both a high molecular specificity
427 (analysis of inorganic and organic species) and imaging capability. Thus, it can provide information
428 on particle sizes, their composition and surface aging [60,89].

429 Finally, laser-based analytical techniques were recently applied in the investigation of aged MPs
430 [73,90]. Direct approaches such as laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS) and laser ablation
431 inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) enable the analysis of aged MPs
432 without requiring specific pre-treatments. LIBS is useful to identify different types of plastics and
433 major elements, whereas LA-ICP-MS is a powerful tool also to monitor the adsorption and leaching
434 of metal traces exploiting the high sensitivity of ICP-MS [73,90]. Synchrotron-based techniques, such
435 as scanning transmission X-ray microscopy (STXM), were also very recently tested for the analysis
436 of aged MPs [91]: these high-resolution techniques may enable the reconstruction of aging
437 mechanisms and give chemical insights within nanometric spatial resolution; however, operational
438 costs and the need for the access to synchrotron facilities limit their broader application.

439

440 **4.2. Characterization of biotic aging**

441 The analysis of biotic aging, especially concerning surface chemical properties and morphology,
442 partially reflects the same techniques implemented for abiotic aging [31]. For example, functional
443 groups of biofilms present on MP fragments may be characterized using FTIR or Raman spectroscopy
444 [92], while changes in surface charge and wettability are analyzed through zeta potential and contact
445 angle measurements, respectively [40]. The attachment of a biofilm on MPs and its morphology may
446 be analyzed using an optical microscope, CLSM [93] or SEM to look more closely at the shape of
447 the microorganisms colonizing the surface of the microplastic [28,33]. Elemental composition of
448 plastic biofilms are also achieved by EDX mapping [28]. In addition, laser based techniques (i.e., LA-
449 ICP-MS, LIBS [73]) are also recently reported to investigate the elemental composition of biofilms
450 on MPs.

451 Beyond physicochemical characterization, there are specific bioanalytical techniques to analyze the
 452 composition and physiological functioning of biofilm on MPs. Quantification of the developed
 453 biofilm, for example, may be done by gravimetric analysis: MPs with developed biofilm are weighed
 454 before and after the biofilm is removed (e.g., by oxidation [33]). Biofilms can also be indirectly
 455 quantified by the determination of proteins as a proxy for the number of microbial cells [94]. Another
 456 approach is based on a staining technique using crystal violet dye: the dye is used to stain the biofilm
 457 and the concentration of the extracted dyes, characterized for example through colorimetry, is linked
 458 to the amount of the extracted biofilm [95].

459 For MPs aged in water, as well as on the surface of soils or sediments, biofilm development can also
 460 be monitored by measuring photosynthetic pigment content [33,96], but this is obviously not relevant
 461 for samples aged in deep soil or wastewater without sunlight [73]. In contrast, the content of EPS can
 462 represent a useful approach for the determination of biofilm. EPS are typical of prokaryotes, but are
 463 also found in some fungi and algae, and play an important role in the attachment of microorganisms
 464 on substrates, including MP surfaces. To reveal the microbial composition of the developed biofilm,
 465 DNA sequencing can be used [31,92,97,98], while the microbial activity of the biofilm can be
 466 measured via activities of various enzymes. For example, Miao et al. [99] followed the oxidizing
 467 capacity of microorganisms in a biofilm towards various carbon sources, while Rozman et al. [33]
 468 determined the activity of ureases as they are commonly found enzymes in many microorganisms.

469

470 Table 1. Physicochemical features and analytical techniques deployed for their analysis to assess the
 471 (biotic or abiotic) aging of MP. Examples of studies using these specific techniques are reported in

472 “References” column.

Feature	Deployed techniques	Biotic- abiotic	References
Size and morphology	Optical microscopy, SEM, TEM, CLSM, AFM	both	[28,30,93]

Surface functional groups	FTIR, Raman spectroscopy, XPS	both	[26,43,47,74,83,100]
Chemical composition	Py-GC-MS, EGA-MS, LIBS, LA-ICP-MS, ToF-SIMS, SEM-EDX, STXM	both	[65,73,74,90]
Surface charge - hydrophobicity	Water contact angle, zeta potential	both	[40,58,100]
Surface area	BET measurements	abiotic	[37,43]
Crystallinity	XRD, Raman, FTIR, TGA-DSC	abiotic	[22,74,101]
Mechanical properties	Elongation tests	abiotic	[26,74]
Thermal properties	TGA-DSC	abiotic	[58,100,102]
Biomass of biofilm	Gravimetric measures, spectroscopic analysis after staining, analysis of proteins	biotic	[40,95]
Biofilm community	DNA analysis, enzyme bioassays, EPS and Chlorophyll analysis	biotic	[33,97,98]

473

474 5. Analytical implications of MP aging

475 Abiotic and biotic aging processes affect all MPs in the environment to some degree. This can have
476 potential important implications not only for their environmental behavior, but on their behavior
477 during analysis. This can complicate their accurate detection and quantification in environmental
478 samples, especially given that particles may represent a wide range of ages induced by different aging
479 processes prior to sampling. Since analytical methods for MPs are often developed and validated
480 using pristine reference MP materials, this potential problem has, thus far, been poorly considered.
481 The changes in surface chemistry and mechanical properties induced by aging may affect the whole
482 analytical workflow for the extraction, clean-up and quantification of MPs in environmental samples
483 (which usually include at least a density separation and a digestion of organic matter prior to the

484 actual analysis, Fig. 3) in an unpredictable way. These issues should be carefully considered both in
485 the setup of new analytical methods and when assessing quality assurance/quality control protocols
486 and harmonization strategies (e.g., to create reference materials [103]).

487

488 **5.1. Potential problems related to extractions and pre-treatments**

489 Sample purification and extraction of MPs is a process extensively used in research and monitoring,
490 especially when determining MP content in complex matrices such as soils, sediments, and biological
491 samples. This normally includes, at least, a density separation step (essentially to remove inorganic
492 particles using concentrated salt solutions) and one or more chemical or enzymatic digestion steps
493 that remove excesses of organic matter in the sample [104–107].

494 First, the enhanced embrittlement of aged MPs can easily induce fragmentation of MPs during the
495 whole analytical protocol, leading to potential artifacts in the measurement. Namely, the chemical
496 treatment or mechanical abrasion induced by sample processing steps may result in the generation of
497 more particles, particularly affecting analyses that result in count-based concentration data. This may
498 also reduce formerly larger particles to smaller fragments that are smaller than the pore sizes of
499 meshes, screens, or filters that are commonly used in sample processing protocols.

500 Aged MPs can also present specific challenges for an effective density separation. Biofouling is
501 known to affect particle density and some issues in the process of density separation have been already
502 highlighted: for instance, Halbach et al. [108] found changes in recovery rates for density separation
503 step after incubation for biofouling on some polymers in a simulated seawater algal community
504 inoculum. Similar problems can obviously emerge also for MP aged in soils or sediments. Another
505 potential issue related to the density separation of aged MPs (both biotically and abiotically), is the
506 different sedimentation rate and hydrophilicity (e.g., [18]). These issues were not assessed yet to the
507 best of our knowledge considering MP extraction and will need specific investigations.

508 Digestion processes are already known to potentially affect different pristine MPs and can have
509 important (and more serious) analytical implications for aged environmental ones [109–111]. As a
510 matter of fact, the reagents used for the removal of organic matter are the same used to simulate
511 abiotic polymer oxidation and hydrolysis (such as H₂O₂ and NaOH). These reagents, when applied
512 on environmentally aged polymers, may more easily create artifacts and have analytical implications,
513 including MP fragmentation with alteration of particle size distribution following treatment during
514 the analysis. A 0.25 M potassium hydroxide (KOH) treatment with sonication for 15 h on 1 cm²
515 square-shaped fragments showed the generation of up to 10⁵ particles in unweathered PLA, PET, and
516 PS [112]. While the processes used for organic matter digestion are often performed under milder
517 treatment conditions than those reported in that study, the increased brittleness of aged MPs compared
518 to pristine polymers may lead to increased fragmentation. In any case, specific investigation into the
519 recoveries of pristine and aged MPs at different grade of aging is necessary to understand the potential
520 of chemical treatments for inhibiting accurate detection and quantification in the final analysis.
521 Similarly, different reagents for MP digestion protocols are known to affect the weight and shape of
522 pristine MPs [105]: this effect can be accentuated in aged MPs. A recent study by Lessa Belone et al.
523 [113] highlighted that abiotically aged MPs composed of different polymers had a higher surface
524 rugosity and fragmentation after a digestion with H₂O₂ at 40 °C for 24h. In addition, they observed a
525 decrease in mass of up to 5% after digestion. These issues may cause under- or overestimation of MP
526 fragments, depending on the size of particles generated and the size detection limits of the techniques
527 used for further counting [75,114].

528 On the other hand, other studies have reported limited issues in digestion procedures when validating
529 their methods using MP particles obtained by environmentally aged samples. For example, a “gentle”
530 digestion of mussels with an enzymatic protocol did not degrade environmentally-collected fragments
531 of low density PE, PP, and expanded PS [115]. Similarly, a study reported the ability to recognize PE
532 fragments in an organic rich sample after digestion with Fenton’s reagent [116]. A more systematic

533 validation of the recovering of different MP typologies affected by different degrees of aging is
 534 needed to confirm these observations and highlight more specifically the conditions where analytical
 535 results may be affected.
 536

537

538 Fig. 3. Scheme of workflow for MPs extraction and analysis from complex media (e.g., a soil
 539 sample) and potential issues for the analysis of environmentally aged MPs. Critical steps likely to
 540 affect results are highlighted in red, while possible issues affecting the measures and requiring
 541 further investigation are indicated in yellow.

542

543 5.2. Potential problems related to analysis

544 Both abiotic and biotic aging can have implications for the effectiveness of particle detection and
 545 quantification, and the determination of chemical composition. Polymer embrittlement driven by
 546 abiotic aging can have negative implications for size analysis and enumeration (as stated in Section
 547 5.1). Namely, particle fragmentation induced by sample processing treatments may transform
 548 particles that were previously above the size detection limit for a given instrument or analysis into

549 particles that now fall below this threshold, resulting in an underestimation of concentrations by
550 techniques that yield count-based data (such as FTIR or Raman spectroscopy).

551 Particle determination by spectroscopic techniques can be affected by abiotic aging too: a loss of
552 spectral information is induced by changes in surface groups and increased rugosity [114]. The
553 problems in polymer determination can be more marked when a preliminary digestion step is applied
554 to remove organic matter: altered FTIR signals are in fact observed with pristine MPs after several
555 digestions steps for organic matter removal on PP and PE [117]. Biotic aging presents also several
556 implications for the chemical characterization of MPs, as the constituents of biofilms on the surface
557 of MPs can interfere with spectroscopic analysis [77]. For example, the high fluorescence of algae
558 within the biofilm may interfere with the use of Raman spectroscopy for chemical characterization
559 of MPs [73] or some constituents of biofilm can be indicated as new functional groups in spectra
560 provided by FTIR analysis [118]. To date, no generalized functions have been developed to correct
561 for this matrix effect and aid in consistent determination. On the other hand, a more thorough removal
562 of organic matter to avoid such a complication, can, as discussed above, affect the quality of the
563 analysis and introduce artifacts.

564 Chemical changes induced by abiotic aging can negatively impact the chemical characterization of
565 MP by mass-spectrometry as well. For example, samples of PE, PS, and PP showed altered chemical
566 markers in their mass-chromatograms using double shot Py-GC/MS [74,87]. Most studies use virgin
567 polymers as standards for calibration, and the change in peak height or area of the selected pyrolysis
568 markers for quantification compared to aged polymers will lead to over- or underestimation of the
569 polymers present. Thus, performing Py-GC/MS on environmental samples without knowing the
570 effect of aging on the polymers present is challenging. Available literature treating this issue only
571 covers a few polymer types and is also limited in the morphology size and chemical content of the
572 material tested. To what extent biofilms present on plastic particles influence the identification and
573 quantification of plastics with Py-GC-MS is, to the best of our knowledge, not yet known. While,

574 hypothetically, this issue should only affect the quantification via Py-GC-MS to a limited degree –
575 owing to the well distinct chemical composition of biomass by-products after pyrolysis (e.g., [119])
576 – this speculation should be validated by evidence. In summary, there is a clear need to consolidate
577 knowledge in this specific area to fully empower Py-GC/MS as a main and reliable analytical tool for
578 MP research.

579

580 **6. Ways forward and recommendations**

581 The issues highlighted in this review showed the need to better understand and, possibly, overcome
582 analytical issues related to the analysis of MPs aged in the environment, especially in soils where
583 photooxidative, biotic, and mechanic aging processes may take place simultaneously. In this chapter
584 we will suggest the possible strategies to overcome some of these issues and we suggest the next steps
585 toward the creation of realistic aged MP reference materials at increasing environmental relevance.

586

587 **6.1. Toward the creation of aged MP reference materials**

588 An important improvement to overcome issues in the analytical assessment of environmental MPs
589 could be introduced by the use of adequate aged reference materials during both validation,
590 calibration (e.g., for Py-GC-MS analysis), and for recovery tests (setting up extraction and
591 purification methods) [21,79]. Some effort has been placed toward the creation of MP reference
592 materials (see e.g., [40,120]). However, the integration of aging processes in this process is still
593 largely overlooked.

594 A key issue for the generation of aged reference materials stands in the harmonization of aging
595 protocols. This is fundamental also for the comparison of findings among studies testing aging
596 processes. For example, considering a common practice such as UV aging, we encourage the detailed
597 description of the UV source (e.g., emitting spectrum and irradiance) and its comparison with the

598 potential equivalence of natural light radiation [26]. We also encourage comparative studies of UV
599 aging conditions and comparison of results with other physicochemical stressors [38].

600 Another important step toward the creation of realistic aged reference materials is the use of MPs that
601 can be obtained with consistent and known chemical formulations. Additive chemicals are in fact
602 commonly added to plastic products and their presence obviously affects physicochemical properties
603 and polymer aging processes [27,40]. We also suggest incorporating biodegradable polymers in
604 studies assessing the effects of biotic and abiotic aging. Considering their emerging and increasing
605 abundance, these polymers will need to be included as references materials for MP analysis [41].

606

607 **6.2. Improving environmental relevance in the simulation of MP aging**

608 Beyond the harmonization of aging simulations, the creation of appropriate reference materials
609 requires realistically mimicking natural aging processes. It is therefore of the utmost importance to
610 recreate the relevant aging pathways more likely to affect MP properties in specific environments
611 [23]. To do so, we suggest to compare different biotic and abiotic aging processes at a time through
612 multi-tiered, laboratory-based experiments [28,55]: this approach permits the ranking effects of
613 different aging processes, as well as testing potential synergistic or antagonistic effects of multiple
614 aging processes at a time, ensuring improved environmental relevance while still permitting tunable
615 and controllable conditions. As an example, the “cover effect” of biofilms on MPs in mediating the
616 chemical properties of its surface (see section 3.1) needs further specific investigation, such as the
617 design of simulated aging processes (e.g., though UV irradiation) before and after the formation of a
618 biofilm on MPs. We also suggest comparing different laboratory- and field-based approaches (e.g.,
619 [22,100,101]), or at least the comparison of simulated aged MPs with environmental samples, to test
620 the environmental relevance of the former.

621

622 **6.3. Alternative analytical approaches for aged MP analyses.**

623 Finally, we suggest other potential analytical alternatives to overcome the analytical issues generated
624 by MP aging. Specific data treatment techniques may overcome some problems; for example, the use
625 of multivariate statistics to classify polymers via FTIR spectroscopy gained satisfying results also
626 using environmentally aged materials [121]. We also suggest exploring the use of direct analytical
627 techniques (e.g., LIBS, LA-ICP-MS, ToF-SIMS), to enable the analysis of MPs that avoids the need
628 for pre-treatments that may induce loss or fragmentation of MPs (e.g., removal of organic matter by
629 digestion). However, the application of these techniques for the analysis of MPs relies on the analysis
630 of chemical markers (e.g., some metallic elements for LIBS and LA-ICP-MS [5,73]) which can be
631 very variable in environmental samples. This hampers their further exploitation in the analysis of
632 environmental MPs.

633

634 **7. Outlook and conclusions**

635 In this review we highlighted the key role of environmental aging of MPs, with a focus on soil and
636 freshwater environments, highlighting both the environmental consequences and the expected
637 implications for their analytical assessment. We showed the current strategies and future steps to
638 simulate environmental aging, highlighting the need for laboratory-based approaches to elucidate the
639 effects of different abiotic and biotic factors in changing the physicochemical proprieties of aged
640 MPs. We also highlighted the current needs to successfully address the environmental implications
641 of MP biotic and abiotic aging (alone and in combination) for the degradation and embrittlement of
642 plastic polymers and the leaching of potentially toxic chemicals from their matrix. We then assessed,
643 for the first time, the potential implications of aging during the analysis of MPs from environmental
644 samples, especially from challenging matrices such as soils. This issue is generally overlooked when
645 calibrating and setting up new protocols. Several critical aspects to be taken into consideration when
646 handling, extracting and analyzing these samples were described here.

647

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656

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